

Exploring Rare Vulvovaginal Lesions: A Series of Case Reports**Kalyani Prava Gouda¹, Pratiksha Mishra², Yugosmita Patra³, Priyadarshini Biswal⁴, Lity Mohanty⁵**¹Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack²Postgraduate, 2nd year, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack³Assistant Professor, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, BBMCH, Bolangir⁵Professor and HOD, Department of Pathology, SCB Medical College, Cuttack

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Abstract:

Pathological lesions in vulva and vagina include a wide range of inflammatory, benign as well as malignant tumors, some of which are challenges for a proper diagnosis. Histopathology has a great and significant role in early and appropriate diagnosis. In the present study, we present four interesting and rare cases involving the female genitalia. The first case is of an elderly female who presented with persistent vulvar eczema. Detailed examination revealed it to be a case of primary cutaneous mucinous carcinoma of vulva, an extremely rare adnexal tumor. The second case was of a young female who presented with a vulvovaginal mass and bleeding per vaginum. Biopsy revealed it to be a case of pleomorphic rhabdomyosarcoma. The third case presented with a right labial mass associated with itching and it was diagnosed to be case of epithelioid sarcoma. The final case was of a young female who presented with multiple black swellings over vulva and was histopathologically diagnosed as vulvar syringoma.

Keywords: Vulvovaginal Lesions, Primary Cutaneous Mucinous Carcinoma, Epithelioid Sarcoma, Pleomorphic Rhabdomyosarcoma, Vulvar Syringoma.

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Introduction**Case Report 1:**

Primary cutaneous mucinous carcinoma (PCMC) is an extremely rare, low grade, adnexal sweat gland neoplasm of eccrine or apocrine origin, that commonly affects the head and neck region of elderly individuals [1,2]. Approximately 200 cases of PCMC have been diagnosed worldwide. [3]. PCMC cases in the vulva are even rarer and possess a diagnostic challenge. Secondary extramammary Paget's disease results from the spread of an underlying adnexal adenocarcinoma or an underlying visceral malignancy, most commonly urothelial or anorectal, but it may also be cervical, prostatic, ovarian, or endometrial.

An 80-year-old female presented with a gradually increasing vulvar swelling of 1.5cm in diameter associated with persistent itching since 8 months. She had no other comorbidities. There was no family history of breast or gynecological malignancy. Her past surgical history was also insignificant. On clinical examination, 1.5cm diameter firm non-tender nodular mass on her left labium majus was present, surrounded by an erythematous, indurated plaque with ulceration.

Multiple firm, non-tender matted left inguinal lymph nodes detected altogether measuring 2.5cm in diameter. Comprehensive blood examinations, laboratory tests, and imaging studies including chest xray and mammography done were unremarkable. With the clinical diagnosis of Bowen's disease and extramammary paget's disease, fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) was done.

FNAC of vulvar mass revealed mildly pleomorphic cells arranged mostly in groups and few singly over pools of mucinous material in the background. Individual cells were round to oval in shape with abundant amount of vacuolated cytoplasm having hyperchromatic nuclei, and occasional prominent nucleoli. Hence, a provisional diagnosis of adnexal skin tumor of low malignant potential was given. FNAC of inguinal node showed mixed population of small and large lymphocytes with numerous tingible body macrophages indicating reactive hyperplasia of lymph node.

Hence skin punch biopsy was done. Microsection showed tumor cell infiltration to epidermis and dermis. Clusters of signet ring cells were arranged

in sheets and singles having abundant vacuolated cytoplasm and eccentrically placed nucleus, floating in pools of extracellular mucin and separated by thin fibro vascular septa.

The epidermis showed irregular hyperplasia with scattered large cells having clear or moderate eosinophilic cytoplasm, arranged mostly in clusters and some singly indicating a pagetoid spread of tumor cells. On immunohistochemistry(IHC), tumor cells showed positivity for cytokeratin-7(CK7), epithelial membrane antigen(EMA), carcinoembryonic antigen(CEA) and gross cystic disease fluid protein(GCDFP)in tumor cells, and

negative for cytokeratin-20(CK20), estrogen receptor protein(ER) and progesterone receptor protein(PR). EMA or MUC1 immunostaining showed positivity for apical mucin secreting portion of tumor cells. The mucin within the cysts was PAS positive. IHC and combined negative clinical examination findings and imaging studies helped us rule out other mucinous and metastatic mucinous lesions of vulva.

So the final diagnosis of primary cutaneous mucinous carcinoma with secondary extra mammary paget's disease (EMPD) of vulva was made.

Figure 1a: A single nodular mass with surrounding erythematous plaque with ulceration, **Fig 1b:** Round to oval cells with pools of mucin, MGG (40x), **Fig 1c:** Pleomorphic cells with hyperchromatic nuclei, MGG (400x), **Fig 1d:** Cells with vacuolated cytoplasm, MGG (400x), **Fig 1e:** Epidermis showing irregular hyperplasia with tumor cells in dermis, H&E (40x), **Fig 1f:** Signet ring cells in sheets and singles, H&E (40x), **Fig 1g:** Vacuolated cells in mucinous background, H&E (100x), **Fig 1h:** Epidermis showing pagetoid spread, H&E (400x), **Fig 1i:** PAS positivity in tumor cells. (400x), **Fig 1j:** IHC, CK7 shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells (400x), **Fig 1k:** IHC, CEA shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells (400x), **Fig 1l:** IHC, shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor EMA cells (400x), **Fig 1m:** IHC, Gcdfp shows focal cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells (400x)

Primary cutaneous mucinous carcinoma also called as adenocystic carcinoma is a rare adnexal tumor. PCMC shows a slight male predominance and typically affects elderly people aged 50–70 years [4]. PCMC most commonly affects the eyelid, followed by scalp, face, axilla, chest/abdominal wall, extremity, groin however PCMC of vulva is even rarer [4]. The PCMC lesions typically present as erythematous, asymptomatic nodules measuring 0.5 to 7 cm in diameter; but, larger variants have also been reported [5]. It is still controversial whether PCMC has eccrine or apocrine origin. There are no clear cut distinguishing features either clinically or histopathologically. However some authors have suggested it to be of apocrine origin because of its tendency to develop in areas having numerous apocrine glands like vulva and scrotum [6]. This indicates PCMC is derived from the follicular-apocrine-sebaceous axis rather than eccrine axis. The presence of decapitation secretion is also another hallmark of apocrine differentiation. However, some reports suggest that apocrine carcinoma can be present without decapitation, and these relied on the identification of tumor cells having abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm and from a typical location including the axilla or groin, as present in our case [6]. Most cases of mucinous carcinoma in the skin are secondary to metastases from breast, gastrointestinal tract, pancreas, bronchi, lung, salivary gland, nose, paranasal sinuses, lacrimal gland, renal pelvis and ovary [8]. Microscopically, it resembles mammary colloid carcinoma wherein the tumor cells are arranged in cell clusters floating in pools of mucin separated by thin fibrovascular septa involving mainly dermis and subcutaneous tissue. The overlying epidermis may be involved with irregular epidermal hyperplasia and pagetoid spread of tumor cells when associated secondary to EMPD. The differentials of this diagnoses includes cutaneous metastases from either breast or colon more likely to be seen in an elderly female. Histologic features such as larger clusters of cohesive neoplastic cells having high nuclear cytoplasmic ratio, fewer quantities of mucin, predominance of epithelium over mucin, and the absence of delicate fibrous septa favors metastasis[4]. However there was no any significant family history of breast cancer and patient's clinical breast examination and mammography done were normal. The normal colonoscopic studies and CK-20 negativity hence ruled out colonic metastases. Therefore, before giving a final diagnosis of primary cutaneous mucinous carcinoma, a thorough search for mucinous carcinoma and metastases from other organs should be done, as was done in our case. Other differentials include Bartholin's gland mucinous carcinoma and mucinous carcinoma arising in ectopic breast tissue, can be distinguished

based on clinical and histopathological basis [4]. Bartholin's gland's adenocarcinoma is usually seen in labia minora and for mucinous carcinoma in ectopic breast tissue, no breast parenchyma was identified histopathologically. EMPD, a rare variant of adenocarcinoma is typically seen involving apocrine glands of vulvar, perianal, perineal, scrotal, and penile regions. EMPD sometimes occurs secondarily in association with cutaneous adnexal tumors or with internal malignancies of endometrium, endocervix, vagina, vulva, urethra, bladder, prostate [4,9]. Among vulval EMPD, 11–20% are associated with underlying visceral malignancy [9]. Some studies have shown that vulvar EMPD was associated with adnexal adenocarcinoma in 4% of cases and with a distant malignancy in 20%. There have been rare cases of PCMC coexisting with overlying EMPD, as in our case. The current management protocol for PCMC includes surgical excision with at least 1cm margin as these cases are resistant to chemotherapy and radiotherapy [7]. Prognosis is relatively good with rare metastases to localized lymph nodes [10]. Close follow up and monitoring is required in elderly individuals because of chances of recurrence seen in 29.4% despite PCMC having a low metastatic rate and gradually progressive course [4]. The overall mortality rate reported till date is 2% [7].

Case Report 2:

A18-year-old female presented with increased vaginal bleeding associated with lower abdominal discomfort which increased rapidly since 4 months. She had no other comorbidities. There was no family history of any malignancy. Her past surgical history was also insignificant. Comprehensive blood examinations, laboratory tests were unremarkable. With the clinical diagnosis of abnormal uterine bleeding due to cervical polyp, Ultrasonography of abdomen and pelvis (USG) revealed heterogeneously enhancing lesion with a surrounding rim of enhancement over anterior vaginal wall raising the query of organized clots/subtissue in vaginal wall., Excisional biopsy was planned and the tissue was sent for histopathological examination. Grossly, multiple greyish brown tissue structures altogether measuring 5x3x2cm was received. Cut section showed solid, yellowish white homogenous areas. Microsection showed tumor cells were arranged in diffuse pattern separated by fibrovascular septa. There was presence of large, polygonal to rhabdoid looking cells, having abundant amount of eosinophilic cytoplasm, eccentrically placed nucleus, coarse clumped chromatin and inconspicuous nucleoli. There was presence of atypical mitosis: 3/10 HPF. With the suspicion of malignant mesenchymal tumor,

immunohistochemistry (IHC) was done. On IHC, tumor cells showed positivity for desmin and negative for myogenin and MYOD1. So the final

diagnosis of pleomorphic rhabdomyosarcoma was made.

Figure 2a: H&E (40X), Microsection shows tumor cells arranged in diffuse sheets separated by fibrovascular septa, Figure 2b: H&E (100X), HPE shows large, polygonal to rhabdoid cells with eccentrically placed nucleus., Figure 2c: H&E (100X), HPE shows large, atypical bizarre looking cells having abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm, eccentrically placed nucleus, Figure 2d: H&E (400X), Desmin shows cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells

Case Report 3:

A 27-year-old female presented with a gradually increasing right labial swelling of 3cm in diameter associated with mild itching since 6 months. She had no other comorbidities. There was no family history of any malignancy. Her past surgical history was also insignificant. On clinical examination, a firm, non-tender, non-ulcerative swelling measuring 3cm in diameter was present over the right labia majus. No significant skin redness or signs of discharge was seen. Comprehensive blood examinations, laboratory tests were unremarkable. With the clinical diagnosis of malignancy, excisional biopsy was planned and the tissue was sent for histopathological examination.

Grossly, skin attached tissue measuring 3cm in diameter was received. Cut section showed solid,

yellowish white homogenous areas. Microsection showed normal keratinized stratified squamous epithelium with underlying tumor tissue. Tumor cells were arranged in diffuse pattern separated by fibrovascular septa. Individual tumor cells were round to polygonal in shape having moderate amount of eosinophilic cytoplasm, round to oval to spindle nucleus having vesicular chromatin and prominent nucleoli. Both typical and atypical mitosis were found, 8/10HPF. Plenty of myxoid areas in between the tumor cells and necrosis was seen. There was presence of numerous multinucleated tumor giant cells. With the suspicion of malignant mesenchymal tumor, immunohistochemistry (IHC) was done. On IHC, tumor cells showed positivity for vimentin, epithelial membrane antigen (EMA) and negative for cytokeratin-7, cytokeratin-20(CK20),

carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) and S100. IHC and combined negative clinical examination findings and imaging studies helped us rule out other mucinous of labia. So the final diagnosis of

epithelioid sarcoma was made. Further the patient was advised for cytogenetic study, for the loss of INI1/SMARCB1 correlation.

Figure 3a: Microsection shows keratinized stratified squamous epithelium, with underlying tumor tissue admixed with myxoid areas. H&E (40X), **Figure 3b:** Individual cells are round to polygonal with moderate eosinophilic cytoplasm, vesicular chromatin and prominent nucleoli. H&E (400X), **Figure 3c:** Vimentin shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells. IHC (400X), **Figure 3d:** EMA shows strong cytoplasmic positivity in tumor cells. IHC (400X)

Case Report 4:

A 22-year-old female presented to the Department of dermatology with gradually increasing multiple brownish black swellings over right vulva, largest measuring 3cm in diameter since 1 year. The lesions were associated with mild itching. She had no other comorbidities. There was no family

history of any malignancy. Her past surgical history was also insignificant. On clinical examination, multiple firm, non-tender, hyperpigmented papules were present over right vulval region, largest measuring 3cm in diameter. No significant skin redness or signs of discharge was seen. Comprehensive blood examinations, laboratory

tests were unremarkable. With the clinical diagnosis of vulvar syringoma, papular acantholytic dyskeratosis of vulva and soft tissue fibroma, excisional biopsy was done and the tissue was sent for histopathological examination. Grossly, skin attached greyish white tissue measuring 3 cm in diameter was received.

Cut section showed homogenous greyish black areas. Microsection showed normal appearing keratinized stratified squamous epithelium with underlying subepithelium showing epithelial cells

arranged in nests, ductules and cysts. All the cysts were lined by squamous epithelium.

Individual tumor cells are composed of benign appearing basaloid cells in a fibrotic stromal background. The tumor tissue showing ducts were lined by double layer of epithelial cells are present in comma and tadpole shaped pattern.

Lumina of some of the ducts showed the presence of keratin flakes. So the final diagnosis of vulvar syringoma was made.

Figure 4a: H&E (40X), Microsection lined by keratinized stratified squamous epithelium with underlying dermis showing ducts, cysts arranged in nested pattern, Figure 4b: H&E (40X), Lining epithelium with underlying dermis showing multiple ductules, Figure 4c: H&E (400X), Keratin flakes in duct lumina, Figure 4d: H&E (400X), the tumor tissue showing ducts were lined by double layer of epithelial cells are present in comma and tadpole shaped pattern

Table 1: Summary of Cases

Cas e No.	Age	Inciden ce	Sympto ms	Clinical findings	Microscop ic findings	Immunohist- ochemistry	Histopathologic al diagnosis
1.	80Yr s	0.02-0.04%	Persisting vulvar eczema for 2 years	1.5x1.5cm itchy lesion	Clusters of signet ring cells and extracellular mucin along with pagetoid spread in epidermis	CK7,EMA,CEA,Gcdp are positive, but CK20, ER, PR showed negative in tumor cells	Primary Cutaneous Mucinous Carcinoma
2.	18Yr s	<2%	Irregular bleeding and abdominal discomfort for 4 months	Growth over anterior vaginal wall and cervix. USG: heterogeneous enhancing lesion with rim of enhancement	Rhabdoid looking pleomorphic polygonal cells with increased mitosis (5/10HPF)	Desmin is positive but Myogenin, MyoD1 are negative in tumor cells	Pleomorphic rhabdomyosarcoma
3.	27Yr s	<5%	Right labial swelling for 6 months	Non tender, non-ulcerative growth measuring 3 cm in diameter	Round to polygonal pleomorphic cells with increased mitosis (8/10HPF), myxoid areas and necrosis, both typical and atypical mitosis seen	Vimentin, EMA shows positivity in tumor cells but CK7,CK20,CEA and S100 is negative	Epithelioid Sarcoma
4.	22Yr s	Rare	Multiple firm vulval lesions associated with itching	Multiple brownish black swelling over right vulva, largest measuring 3 cm in diameter (hyperpigmented papules)	Epidermis with subepidermal cells in nests, ductules and cysts. Tumor cells are basaloid with a fibrotic stroma in background	-	Vulvar syringoma

Discussion

Primary Cutaneous Mucinous Carcinoma also called as adenocystic carcinoma is a rare adnexal tumor. It is still controversial whether it has got apocrine or eccrine origin, without any clear distinguishing histopathological features. It has to

be distinguished from cutaneous metastases from breast or colon [4], especially in an elderly female. The current management protocol includes surgical excision with at least 1cm margin as they are very resistant lesions with chances of recurrences in 29.4% cases [4]. Kelly BC et al and Sur-ju oh et al also reported PCMC in vulva similar to our case

[2,4] Pleomorphic rhabdomyosarcoma is commonly seen in young females, as was seen in our case. Histopathology and IHC studies help in the diagnosis. It has a poor prognosis, but early diagnosis and treatment helps in a prolonged disease free survival. However follow up of 6 months in the present case was uneventful. Pan Xu et al have also reported pleomorphic rhabdomyosarcoma in vagina [11].

Vulvar epithelioid sarcoma is a rare and aggressive soft tissue neoplasm, originally described in 1970, comprising less than 5% of all vulvar neoplasms. Median age is 34 years, ours being 27 years. Histopathology and IHC helps us in ruling out adenocarcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma. Presently SMARCB1 is very helpful in diagnosis, negative S100 helped in ruling out a myoepithelial tumor with myxoid changes [12]. Vulvar syringoma is an underreported entity, likely to be misdiagnosed and is in the differential of popular vulvar eruptions. Histopathology is the mainstay in diagnosis. Most common sites are eyelids, and malar area, vulva being a rare location [13].

Conclusion

Diagnosing different vulvovaginal lesions like PCMC, epithelioid sarcoma, vulvar syringoma, and pleomorphic rhabdomyosarcoma poses challenges due to its rarity and uncommon location, often necessitating consideration of various differential diagnoses. Further studies are required to clarify the origin of PCMC case whether eccrine or apocrine. Hence a detailed laboratory investigation including imaging studies and pathological diagnosis is required before coming into a final diagnosis of any vulvovaginal lesion.

Diagnosis of epithelioid sarcoma is also quite challenging which requires precise histopathology and IHC studies. Pleomorphic rhabdomyosarcoma also requires ancillary IHC studies, apart from histopathology. Diagnosis of syringoma required histopathological examination in detail as difficulty was faced due to its rarity at that site. Hence detailed clinical examination, histopathology and IHC studies observed in detail for a definite and precise diagnosis of some rare vulvovaginal cases.

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